

Finding the Covering radius of codes over \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} by assigning Homogeneous weight

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Abstract: In this paper, lower bound and upper bound on the covering radius of codes over \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} , by assigning Homogeneous weight are found. The covering radius are also found for various repetition codes.

Key words: Codes over finite ring, Covering radius, Generator matrix, Homogeneous weight.

1. Introduction

In the last three decade, much researchers have more interest in codes over finite rings and the recent years, especially in the rings \mathbb{Z}_{2k} , where $2k$ is the ring of integers modulo $2k$. In several papers have mentioned codes over \mathbb{Z}_4 received much attention [1, 4–8]. Good binary linear and non-linear codes can be obtained from codes over \mathbb{Z}_4 via the gray map. Ref.[2, 3, 10–12], the covering radius of binary linear codes are studied. The author gave upper and lower bounds on the covering radius of codes over \mathbb{Z}_{2^3} has been investigated with assigned to Lee distance and Homogeneous distance [9]. In this paper, I obtain the covering radius of some particular codes over \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} . I consider the finite ring \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} of intergers modulo 3^2 in this paper.

2. Preliminaries

Let $C \subseteq \mathbb{Z}_{3^2}^n$ is called a code and C is subspace of $\mathbb{Z}_{3^2}^n$ is said to be \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} -linear code, where \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} is an submodule of $\mathbb{Z}_{3^2}^n$, where n is an length of the code. The elements of C is called a codeword of C . The number of non-zero components in a codeword c is said to be Hamming weight and it is denoted by $wt_H(c)$ and the smallest weight of all the non-zero codewords in a Code C is called a minimum Hamming weight $wt_H(C)$ of a code C .

Let $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2}^n$, where $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ and $y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)$, the minimum distance of code C is $d(C) = \min\{d(x, y) | x, y \in C, x - y \neq 0 \in C\} = \min\{wt(x - y) | x - y \neq 0 \in C\} = \min\{wt(c) | c \in C \neq 0\} = wt_H(C)$ is said to be *Hamming distance* between any distinct vectors $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2}^n$ and is denoted by $d_H(x, y) = wt_H(x - y)$. The minimum Hamming distance between distinct pairs of codewords of a code C and denoted by $d_H(C) = wt_H(C)$.

In[14], the homogeneous weight as given

$$w_{hom}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 3 & \text{if } x = 3, 6 \\ 2 & \text{if otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

3. Covering radius of code and repetition code

In \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} ,

$$r_d(C) = \max_{u \in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2}^n} \left\{ \min_{c \in C} \{d(u, c)\} \right\},$$

where C is a code and $r_d(C)$ is a covering radius of the code C with homogeneous distance(d).

Let C be a q -ary repetition code C over \mathbb{F}_q , where \mathbb{F}_q is a finite field consists of the $\{0, 1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_{q-1}\}$ and the parameters of the code $C = \{\bar{\alpha} | \alpha \in \mathbb{F}_q\}$, where $\bar{\alpha} = \alpha\alpha \dots \alpha$ is an $[n, 1, n]$ code. Use to ref [13], that the covering radius of the code C is $\lfloor \frac{n(q-1)}{q} \rfloor$.

The parameters of the block repetition code C of size n , with $[n(q-1), 1, n(q-1)]$ be a generated by $G = \left[\overbrace{11 \dots 1}^n \overbrace{\alpha_2 \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_2}^n \dots \overbrace{\alpha_{q-1} \alpha_{q-1} \dots \alpha_{q-1}}^n \right]$. Use to ref [13], that the covering radius of the code C is $\lfloor \frac{n(q-1)^2}{q} \rfloor$, since it will be equivalent to a repetition code of length $(q-1)n$.

Consider the repetition code over \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} , there are two type of repetition codes of length n viz.

1. Type I- repetition code:

Let $G_I = \left[\overbrace{11 \dots 1}^n \right]$ be a Generator matrix with unit element in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} . This Generator matrix generated by the code C_I of the parameters $[n, 1, 2n]$, where $2n$ is a minimum homogeneous distance.

2. Type II- repetition code:

Let $G_{II} = \left[\overbrace{33 \dots 3}^n \right]$, $\left[\overbrace{3 \ 6 \ 3 \ 6 \dots 3 \ 6}^n \right]$ or $\left[\overbrace{6 \ 3 \ 6 \ 3 \dots 6 \ 3}^n \right]$ and $\left[\overbrace{66 \dots 6}^n \right]$ are the Generator matrix with zero divisor element in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} . This Generator matrix generated by the code C_{II} of the parameters $(n, 3, 3n)$, where $3n$ is a minimum homogeneous distance.

The following result determines the covering radius with respect to Homogeneous distance.

Theorem 3.1. $r_{hom}(C_I) = 2n$, $\frac{3n}{2} \leq r_{hom}(C_{II}) \leq 2n$.

Proof. Let $x \in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2}^n$ with γ_0 times 0's, γ_1 times 1's, γ_2 times 2's, γ_3 times 3's, γ_4 times 4's, γ_5 times 5's, γ_6 times 6's, γ_7 times 7's, γ_8 times 8's, in x and $\gamma_0 + \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + \gamma_3 + \gamma_4 + \gamma_5 + \gamma_6 + \gamma_7 + \gamma_8 = n$. The code $c_i, i=0$ to $8 \in \{\alpha(C_I) | \alpha \in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2}\}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} d_{hom}(x, c_0) &= wt_{hom}(x - 00 \dots 0) \\ &= 0\gamma_0 + 1\gamma_1 + 2\gamma_2 + 3\gamma_3 + 4\gamma_4 + 5\gamma_5 + 6\gamma_6 + 7\gamma_7 + 8\gamma_8 \\ &= 2\gamma_1 + 2\gamma_2 + 3\gamma_3 + 2\gamma_4 + 2\gamma_5 + 3\gamma_6 + 2\gamma_7 + 2\gamma_8 \\ d_{hom}(x, c_0) &= n - \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + 2\gamma_3 + \gamma_4 + \gamma_5 + 2\gamma_6 + \gamma_7 + \gamma_8. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $d_{hom}(x, c_1) = n - \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + \gamma_3 + 2\gamma_4 + \gamma_5 + \gamma_6 + 2\gamma_7 + \gamma_8 + \gamma_0$. $d_{hom}(x, c_2) = n - \gamma_2 + \gamma_3 + \gamma_4 + 2\gamma_5 + \gamma_6 + \gamma_7 + 2\gamma_8 + \gamma_0 + \gamma_1$. $d_{hom}(x, c_3) = n - \gamma_3 + \gamma_4 + \gamma_5 + 2\gamma_6 + \gamma_7 + \gamma_8 + 2\gamma_0 + \gamma_1 + \gamma_2$. $d_{hom}(x, c_4) = n - \gamma_4 + \gamma_5 + \gamma_6 + 2\gamma_7 + \gamma_8 + \gamma_0 + 2\gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + \gamma_3$. $d_{hom}(x, c_5) = n - \gamma_5 + \gamma_6 + \gamma_7 + 2\gamma_8 + \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 + 2\gamma_2 + \gamma_3 + \gamma_4$. $d_{hom}(x, c_6) = n - \gamma_6 + \gamma_7 + \gamma_8 + 2\gamma_0 + \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + 2\gamma_3 + \gamma_4 + \gamma_5$. $d_{hom}(x, c_7) = n - \gamma_7 + \gamma_8 + \gamma_0 + 2\gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + \gamma_3 + 2\gamma_4 + \gamma_5 + \gamma_6$. $d_{hom}(x, c_8) = n - \gamma_8 + \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 + 2\gamma_2 + \gamma_3 + \gamma_4 + 2\gamma_5 + \gamma_6 + \gamma_7$.

Therefore, $d_{hom}(x, C_I) = \min\{d_{hom}(x, c_0), d_{hom}(x, c_1), d_{hom}(x, c_2), d_{hom}(x, c_3), d_{hom}(x, c_4), d_{hom}(x, c_5), d_{hom}(x, c_6), d_{hom}(x, c_7), d_{hom}(x, c_8)\} \leq n + \frac{9n}{9} = 2n$, where $\gamma_0 + \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + \gamma_3 + \gamma_4 + \gamma_5 + \gamma_6 + \gamma_7 + \gamma_8 = n$. Therefore, $r_{hom}(C_I) \leq 2n$.

Consider

$x = \overbrace{00 \dots 0}^s \overbrace{11 \dots 1}^s \overbrace{22 \dots 2}^s \overbrace{33 \dots 3}^s \overbrace{44 \dots 4}^s \overbrace{55 \dots 5}^s \overbrace{66 \dots 6}^s \overbrace{77 \dots 7}^s \overbrace{88 \dots 8}^{n-8s} \in \mathbb{Z}_{32}^n$, where $s = \lfloor \frac{n}{32} \rfloor$, then $d_{hom}(x, c_0) = 2n$, $d_{hom}(x, c_1) = 2n$, $d_{hom}(x, c_2) = 2n$, $d_{hom}(x, c_3) = 2n$, $d_{hom}(x, c_4) = 2n$, $d_{hom}(x, c_5) = 2n$, $d_{hom}(x, c_6) = 2n$, $d_{hom}(x, c_7) = 2n$ and $d_{hom}(x, c_8) = 2n$. $\therefore r_{hom}(C) \geq \min\{2n, 2n, 2n\} = 2n \geq 2n$. Thus $r_{hom}(C_I) = 2n$.

Let $x = \overbrace{33 \dots 3}^{\frac{n}{2}} \overbrace{000 \dots 0}^{\frac{n}{2}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{32}^n$. The code $C_{II} = \{\alpha(33 \dots 3) \mid \alpha \in \mathbb{Z}_{32}^n\}$, that is $C_{II} = \{00 \dots 0, 33 \dots 3, 66 \dots 6\}$,

generated by $[33 \dots 3]$ is an $(n, 3, 3n)$ code. Then, $d_{hom}(x, 00 \dots 0) = wt_{hom}(\overbrace{33 \dots 3}^{\frac{n}{2}} \overbrace{000 \dots 0}^{\frac{n}{2}} - 00 \dots 0) =$

$\frac{n}{2} wt_{hom}(3) = \frac{3n}{2}$, $d_{hom}(x, 33 \dots 3) = wt_{hom}(\overbrace{33 \dots 3}^{\frac{n}{2}} \overbrace{000 \dots 0}^{\frac{n}{2}} - 33 \dots 3) = \frac{n}{2} wt_{hom}(6) = \frac{3n}{2}$, and $d_{hom}(x, 66 \dots 6) =$

$wt_{hom}(\overbrace{33 \dots 3}^{\frac{n}{2}} \overbrace{000 \dots 0}^{\frac{n}{2}} - 66 \dots 6) = \frac{n}{2} wt_{hom}(6) + \frac{n}{2} wt_{hom}(3) = 3n$. Therefore, $d_{hom}(x, C_{II}) = \min\{\frac{3n}{2}, 3n\} = \frac{3n}{2}$.

Thus, $r_{hom}(C_{II}) \geq \frac{3n}{2}$.

Let $x \in \mathbb{Z}_{32}^n$ be any codeword and take x has γ_0 links as 0's, γ_1 links as 1's, γ_2 links as 2's, γ_3 links as 3's, γ_4 links as 4's, γ_5 links as 5's, γ_6 links as 6's, γ_7 links as 7's and γ_8 links as 8's, with $\gamma_0 + \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + \gamma_3 + \gamma_4 + \gamma_5 + \gamma_6 + \gamma_7 + \gamma_8 = n$. Since $C_{II} = \{00 \dots 0, 33 \dots 3, 66 \dots 6\}$. So, $r_{hom}(C_{II}) \leq 2n$. Hence, $\frac{3n}{2} \leq r_{hom}(C_{II}) \leq 2n$. □

4. Block repetition code for the same size of length(n)

In this section, the covering radius for the same size of block repetition code C of a length(n) with respect to Homogeneous weight is given.

The same size of length(n) of the block repetition code C of a parameters $[6n, 1, 12n,]$, that is $BRep^{6n} : [6n, 1, 12n]$ is generated by

$$G_1 = [\overbrace{11 \dots 1}^n \overbrace{22 \dots 2}^n \overbrace{44 \dots 4}^n \overbrace{55 \dots 5}^n \overbrace{77 \dots 7}^n \overbrace{88 \dots 8}^n] \quad (1)$$

and get below

Theorem 4.1. *Prove the following*

1. $r_{hom}(BRep^{6n}) = 12n$.

2. $\frac{7n}{2} \leq r_{hom}(BRep^{2n}) \leq 4n$ in $G = [\overbrace{11 \dots 1}^n \overbrace{33 \dots 3}^n]$.

Proof. In (1) and [10] and use to theorem (3.1), then

$$r_{hom}(BRep^{6n}) \geq 12n \quad (2)$$

let $y = (z_1 | z_2 | z_3 | z_4 | z_5 | z_6) \in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2}^{6n}$, where $z_i \in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2}^{6n}, i = 1$ to 6. Let us take in u_1 , 0 appears r_0 times, 1 appears r_1 times, 2 appears r_2 times 3 appears r_3 times 4 appears r_4 times, 5 appears r_5 times, 6 appears r_6 times, 7 appears r_7 times and 8 appears r_8 times, in u_2 , j appears s_j times, in u_3 , j appears t_j times, in u_4 , j appears v_j times, in u_5 , j appears u_j times, in u_6 , j appears w_j times, with $\sum_j r_j = \sum_j s_j = \sum_j t_j = n = \sum_j v_j = \sum_j u_j = \sum_j w_j$ and $c_j \in \{\alpha(G_1) | \alpha \in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2}^{6n}\}, j = 0$ to 8.

Then, $d_{hom}(y, BRep^{6n}) = \min\{d_{hom}(y, c_j) | j = 0$ to 8 $\}$ is less than or equal to $6n + \frac{6n+6n+6n+6n+6n+6n+6n+6n+6n}{9} = 12n$. Thus, $d_{hom}(y, BRep^{6n}) \leq 12n$. Hence,

$$r_{hom}(BRep^{6n}) \leq 12n \tag{3}$$

By (2) and (3), the following results is obtained,

$$r_{hom}(BRep^{6n}) = 12n.$$

The Proof of second part is follows from first part and so, $\frac{7n}{2} \leq r_{hom}(BRep^{2n}) \leq 4n$. □

5. Bolck repetition code with different size of the length (m_1, m_2)

In this section, only detail that the covering radius are found for different size of block repetition code with assigned to Homogeneous weight.

There are two different size of length (m_1, m_2) of the block repetition code C in \mathbb{Z}_{3^2} , $BRep^{m_1+m_2}$: $[m_1 + m_2, 1, \min\{2m_1, 2m_1 + 3m_2\}]$ generated by $G_3 = [\overbrace{11 \cdots 1}^{m_1} \overbrace{33 \cdots 3}^{m_2}]$ and also found the following

Theorem 5.1. Show that $2m_1 + m_2 \leq r_{hom}(BRep^{m_1+m_2}) \leq 2m_1 + 2m_2$.

Proof. Use to Theorem (4.1) and apply the two different size of length (m_1, m_2) . □

In general, the Block repetition code for six different size of length

$BRep^{m_1+m_2+m_3+m_4+m_5+m_6}$: $[m_1 + m_2 + m_3 + m_4 + m_5 + m_6, 1, \min\{2(m_1 + m_2 + m_3 + m_4 + m_5 + m_6), 3(m_1 + m_2 + m_3 + m_4 + m_5 + m_6)\}]$ generated by $G_4 = [\overbrace{11 \cdots 1}^{m_1} \overbrace{22 \cdots 2}^{m_2} \overbrace{44 \cdots 4}^{m_3} \overbrace{55 \cdots 5}^{m_4} \overbrace{77 \cdots 7}^{m_5} \overbrace{88 \cdots 8}^{m_6}]$. I obtain, the following

Theorem 5.2. Find the relation for $r_{hom}(BRep^{m_1+m_2+m_3+m_4+m_5+m_6})$.

Proof. By making use of the theorem (5.1), it can be prove

$$r_{hom}(BRep^{m_1+m_2+m_3+m_4+m_5+m_6}) = 2(m_1 + m_2 + m_3 + m_4 + m_5 + m_6). \tag{4} \quad \square$$

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